

Evaluating Clinical Judgment in Licensure Tests: Applications of Decision Theory

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Accurately classifying candidates according to their competencies is essential to all licensure exams. Misclassifying candidates in high stakes professions—for example, in health professions—can lead to dramatic consequences with far reaching effects. As a way of preventing inappropriately licensing candidates, programs focus on strengthening methods that test the basic knowledge and skills required to achieve minimal competency. In particular, licensure programs are giving more attention to higher order cognitive constructs like logical reasoning, judgment, and decision-making (see Lai, 2011).

In professions where making judgments and decisions is fundamental, such as in the health, medical, and financial fields, licensure exams must ensure that passing candidates have sufficient skills to make context-specific decisions or judgments (cf. Simmons, Lanuza, Fonteyn, Hicks, & Holm, 2003). The current paper discusses steps the National Council of State Boards of Nursing (NCSBN, 2015) took when exploring methods that evaluate candidates' decision-making ability (P. Dickison, personal communication, 2014; Muntean, 2012). NCSBN's goal was to define a construct of clinical judgment that is operationalizable, assessable, and measureable. Although we provide an application in clinical judgment, our methodological approach generalizes to many diverse areas of professional licensure.

Theoretical Framework

Most licensure exams seek to identify a level of knowledge and skill that minimally competent practitioners would need in order to function adequately in their new professional endeavors. In all but the simplest of professions, a hierarchy of knowledge and skills occurs naturally and are often referred to as subdomains of the profession. Perhaps the most widely used approach to identify a hierarchy of skills is to carry out a job task analysis. In its basic form, a job task analysis surveys SMEs according to tasks common among the profession (Kane, 2001). Afterwards, test developers cluster the task statements and any other related information (Kirwan & Ainsworth, 1992). The final product is a test plan, with the subdomains classified by their prevalence and/or importance. This practice ensures a licensure exam appropriately assesses the prerequisites to entering a profession.

This should be very familiar to exam developers—it is the genesis of all licensure exams. However, it bears mentioning because a job task analysis is also vital when enhancing a current exam. Before surveying SMEs about the prevalence or frequency of a new construct, such as clinical judgment,

logical reasoning, or decision-making, test developers must take on a theoretical perspective and investigate complex constructs through constrained theoretical models. These models reduce complexity and help focus job task analyses to target construct relevant information (Kirwan & Ainsworth, 1992).

In this paper, we demonstrate the usefulness of maintaining a theoretical framework to identify a cognitive construct. NCSBN used this approach when developing a clinical judgment model (P. Dickison, personal communication, 2014; Muntean, 2012) and we use their procedure as an illustration throughout this paper. When clinical problems become ill-constrained and ambiguous, uncertainty increases and this requires a level of judgment and decision-making (Lamond & Thompson, 2000). However, clinicians must use prerequisite knowledge and skills to guide them when organizing information, and because of this, NCSBN focused on decision-making that is situated within context-specific conditions (Medin, & Schaffer, 1978; Hamm, 1988; Kruglanski & Mayseless, 1988). The construct of decision-making is universal in that decisions are made in all types of professions (clinicians diagnosis: Botti & Reeve, 2003; auditors: Libby, 1995; mechanics: Mehle, 1982; scientists: Fischhoff, 1977). Each discipline, though, needs to specify how to implement a decision-making model within its testing program. Specification should maximize fidelity and ecological validity. This is to say that, although decision-making is common to all professions, programs need to focus on the decision-making aspects most relevant to their profession. The current paper focuses on a clinical model and tailors a decision-making model accordingly (Elstein, Shulman, Sprafka, & Allal, 1978). We therefore refer to this type of decision-making as clinical judgment.

A Clinical Model

Choosing which decision-making model to operate under is the initial and most important step in assessing decision-making ability. Models differ in their underlying assumptions and their level of specificity, all of which vary as a function of many factors (for a review, see Busemeyer & Diederich, 2010). By and large, licensure programs are interested in assessing novice decision-making (e.g., entry-level professionals), and endorsing models that explain novice behavior is thus attractive. Describing decision-making by using a process model allows specification of the mental components involved in decision-making and the interactions between them. To be most useful, a process model must be well specified, with assumptions clearly defined. A well-specified model provides the framework for assessment, measurement, and isolation of decision-making errors.

A fruitful approach is to begin with a well-specified model, reduce its specification and complexity as needed, and then, contextualize it to suit a particular domain (Klein, Orasanu, Calderwood, & Zsombok, 1993). Accordingly, we used this approach when designing the decision-making model presented in this paper. A well-specified but mathematically complex model was reduced to only the vital mental processes involved in decision-making (for the full model, see Thomas, Dougherty, Sprenger, & Harbison, 2008; for an accessible review, and one pertaining to many domains, see Thomas, Dougherty, & Buttaccio, 2014). By supplementing the base model with essential components of clinical decision-making, we created the parsimonious and measurable model of clinical judgment discussed below.

Although assessing cognitive processes is challenging, specifying assumptions reduces the complexity of the task. The first assumption in the clinical judgment model is that the world is represented as a set of external events; through learning and experience, a decision maker internalizes these events. Thereafter, the internalized events become hypotheses (Thomas et al., 2008; Elstein et al., 1978; Dougherty & Hunter, 2003; Gettys & Fisher, 1979). For instance, an external event is the association between a high body temperature and influenza (i.e., the flu). Once a clinician learns and internalizes this external event, it becomes an internal hypothesis. In the future, encountering patients with high temperatures will activate this hypothesis about the association between a high body temperature and the flu. Under realistic conditions, some similarity, co-occurrence, or other related semantic overlap clusters together with external events and internalized hypotheses. Because of this clustering, highly similar but distinct hypotheses become strong competitors for explaining an external event; consequently, a decision maker must distinguish between these competing hypotheses (Windschitl & Wells, 1998). When competing hypotheses are not perfectly distinguishable, a decision maker judges the likelihood of each activated hypothesis and chooses the most plausible candidate (cf., Koehler, Brenner, Liberman, & Tversky, 1996). However, before a decision maker engages in this and subsequent processes, a clinical judgment begins with the step of cue recognition.

Figure 1. Clinical judgment process model.

NCSBN developed the model seen in Figure 1 to describe a clinician entering a situation demanding a decision. Here, the clinician must recognize the cues associated with the clinical problem (Reed, 1972; cue recognition). Using domain-specific knowledge, clinicians must recognize relevant information and discard or ignore irrelevant information. Lapses at this stage of clinical judgment can be characterized by two opposing behaviors. A decision maker overwhelmed with information classifies too many cues as relevant. By contrast, a decision maker with poor knowledge classifies too few cues as relevant. Although for different reasons, decision makers expressing these behaviors have a difficult time with the next stage of decision-making—generating hypotheses.

Hypotheses are activated and generated based on the cue inputs (i.e., generate hypotheses in Figure 1). Because of cognitive limitations, only a subset of hypotheses receives focus (Elstein et al., 1978; Dougherty, Gettys, & Thomas, 1997; Gettys, Pliske, Manning, & Casey, 1987). Over-endorsing cues as relevant increases the propensity to activate and focus on incorrect hypotheses. Likewise, fixating on an incomplete subset of relevant information activates misleading and incorrect hypotheses. However, it is possible to endorse all the correct cues and reject all the incorrect cues—demonstrating perfect cue recognition—but still activate incorrect hypotheses. These three deviations from normative behavior demonstrate the advantage of assessing decision-making through a process model: Decision-making errors can be ranked, weighted, or classified by severity, and the order of severity can differ across professions and licensure programs.

Once hypothesis generation has ceased, the activated hypotheses are judged and ranked on several attributes. The most common ranking dimension is on the likelihood that the hypothesis explains the external event (Tversky & Koehler, 1994). However, ranking may occur on other attributes such as recent

experience or encounters with similar hypotheses or cues, which can bias hypothesis likelihood. When the biases are pronounced, a decision maker will endorse an incorrect hypothesis and proceed to the next step in the model, propagating the error.

With a leading hypothesis in active memory, a clinician will attempt to resolve the current decision problem by taking an action. In the simplest case, a hypothesis will be associated with a single action; when it is judged as most likely, only one outcome follows naturally. In more complicated scenarios, however, a hypothesis may be associated with several reasonable actions. In these situations, a decision maker will activate and generate a set of reasonable actions and rank them on a different set of attributes. This is represented by an inner red loop in Figure 1. Thus, much like hypothesis generation and hypothesis judgment, the same underlying mental processes occur for generating and ranking a set of reasonable actions. It is important to note that a non-action, such as waiting and collecting more information (e.g., hypothesis guided search; Thomas et al., 2008), is itself an action.

An essential component unique to clinical judgment is the evaluation of a decision (Lewis, 1997). A clinician cannot correctly resolve a problem until this has occurred. Complicating matters, the timing of evaluation varies with the problem set. On some occasions, observable outcomes occur immediately after an action, but on other occasions, delayed observable effects require a decision maker to revisit the decision task later. These temporal dynamics complicate clinical decision problems and make them quite challenging. However, once the clinician has evaluated outcomes and produced desirable effects, the clinician can successfully end the task. This is graphically indicated by the backslashes (//) in Figure 1.

If an action produces an undesirable outcome, decision makers cannot appropriately end the decision task. Instead, they observe the new data produced by their actions and feed that information back into the decision process, beginning a new iteration. This iterative approach explains how some decision makers require additional information to reach a final successful outcome. Thus, while the final outcome of a decision problem might be similar between two decision makers, the fluent decision maker proceeds through the process with fewer iterations.

Conclusion

From a pragmatic perspective, a program may not find it essential to tease apart the underlying processes involved in decision-making; instead, it may focus solely on the final outcome of a decision. The

strength of this approach is that it reduces the number of assumptions made. The only vital assumption is that a rational and normative decision occurred when endorsing the correct outcome—homogeneity in the decision-making process. However, this assumption does not seem practical and sidesteps the general goal of measuring individual differences in decision-making ability. By contrast, a process model measures several components of decision-making, allowing a decision maker to fail at particular stages and engage in several mental iterations before reaching a correct outcome. Thus, while the outcome might be the same between two decision makers, one might have a more efficient process.

Clinicians make clinical judgments that combine their context-sensitive knowledge with their decision-making ability as an integral part of their work. However, decision-making is an elusive construct. Describing decision-making as a process provides a granular method for assessing a decision maker's covert thoughts by measuring them at multiple points, thereby isolating errors in the decision maker's reasoning (Lee, 2011). The principal steps in the clinical judgment process are cue recognition, hypothesis generation, hypothesis evaluation, taking an action, and evaluating the outcome.

Additionally, a process model provides a springboard for test developers to begin designing assessments that tap this important construct. Standard item types such as multiple choice items can assess certain steps in the process, such as cue recognition, and they can assess the process as a whole but cannot isolate errors in reasoning. Technology-enhanced items remove these limitations. They can either measure the clinical process as a whole, tracking errors within the process, or measure all of the discrete steps separately. Therefore, obtaining information from examinees depends upon item types that already exist, making it easier for content developers and subject-matter experts to focus instead on the application of a decision-making model within their field.

The present theoretical position resulted in a flexible decision-making model that expresses the complexities associated with decision-making in a simplified manner. This simplification provides NCSBN a process model that highlights the most important decision-making subcomponents when making clinical judgments. Because the model is well-specified, it provides a firm basis for developing items that evaluate candidates' clinical judgment. Bridging theory and practice, a process model lends itself to application across diverse licensure testing programs.

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